

No.	Date	Sex	Age	Subgroup	Diagnostic methods	DOB/DPM	Review results	Number of tablets left	Side effects/others
1	1.2	female	54	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	7.3	negative	0	
2	1.4	female	57	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	29.7	negative	3	
3	1.6	female	48	the control group	13C-UBT	21.9	negative	0	
4	1.12	male	54	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	36.2	negative	0	
5	1.18	female	59	the control group	13C-UBT	19.2	negative	0	
6	1.20	female	53	the control group	13C-UBT	12.5	positive	0	
7	1.25	male	45	the control group	13C-UBT	20.8	negative	0	Diarrhea
8	2.15	male	41	the control group	13C-UBT	28.7	negative	0	
9	2.25	male	48	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	11.4	negative	0	
10	2.25	male	52	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	10.7	negative	0	
11	2.26	female	57	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	41.9	positive	1	
12	2.26	female	32	the control group	13C-UBT	7.3	negative	0	

13	2.27	male	57	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	7.6	negative	0	
14	3.1	male	26	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	64.2	negative	0	
15	3.4	male	45	the control group	13C-UBT	13.0	negative	4	
16	3.4	male	25	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	10.8	negative	0	
17	3.8	male	59	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	14.8	negative	0	
18	3.8	female	57	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	23.3	negative	0	
19	3.15	female	53	the control group	13C-UBT	32.0	positive	120	skin rash ; nausea
20	3.19	male	35	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	28.5	negative	0	Slight diarrhea
21	3.25	female	34	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	22.3	negative	0	
22	3.25	male	46	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	28.7	negative	0	
23	3.27	female	61	the control group	13C-UBT	18.6	negative	0	
24	3.27	male	33	the control group	13C-UBT	67.4	negative	0	
25	3.27	female	51	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	37.9	negative	0	

26	3.29	female	34	the control group	13C-UBT	12.9	positive	158	poor appetite ;melena ; nausea
27	4.1	male	34	the control group	13C-UBT	20	negative	3	
28	4.3	female	36	the control group	13C-UBT	23.4	negative	7	
29	4.8	female	24	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	37.2	negative	0	
30	4.16	male	33	the control group	13C-UBT	20.5	negative	0	
31	4.22	male	63	the control group	13C-UBT	18.5	negative	0	nausea
32	4.23	female	30	the control group	13C-UBT	17.8	negative	0	
33	4.24	male	34	the control group	13C-UBT	62.7	negative	0	Poor appetite
34	4.24	male	49	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	17.7	negative	0	Mild nausea
35	4.24	female	28	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	7.8	negative	12	
36	4.29	female	24	the control group	13C-UBT	58.4	positive	12	
37	4.29	female	48	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	21.5	negative	5	
38	4.30	male	34	the control group	13C-UBT	11.7	negative	0	

39	5.5	male	41	the control group	13C-UBT	18.7	negative	0	
40	5.7	male	36	the control group	13C-UBT	88.6	negative	0	
41	5.8	male	54	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	35.4	negative	0	
42	5.8	female	29	the control group	13C-UBT	39.1	positive	3	
43	5.1	male	24	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	19.6	negative	0	Poor appetite
44	5.1	male	31	the control group	13C-UBT	21	negative	6	Poor appetite
45	5.3	male	24	intensive follow-up group	14C-UBT	1415	negative	0	
46	5.3	female	40	the control group	13C-UBT	23.9	negative	0	
47	5.3	male	31	the control group	13C-UBT	24.0	negative	0	
48	5.7	male	36	the control group	13C-UBT	26.1	negative	0	
49	5.8	female	30	the control group	13C-UBT	41.5	positive	114	bitter taste; melena
50	5.8	female	41	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	13.9	negative	0	
51	5.8	female	56	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	8.8	positive	0	

52	5.8	female	37	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	30.3	negative	0	
53	5.8	male	50	the control group	13C-UBT	58	negative	0	
54	5.9	male	40	the control group	13C-UBT	62.4	negative	0	
55	5.1	male	63	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	29.5	negative	0	
56	5.14	male	22	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	9.2	negative	0	
57	5.16	female	63	the control group	13C-UBT	46.7	negative	0	nausea
58	5.16	male	60	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	18.9	negative	0	Mild nausea
59	5.17	male	66	the control group	13C-UBT	30.5	negative	0	
60	5.2	female	43	the control group	13C-UBT	29.9	negative	0	
61	5.21	male	60	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	30.7	negative	9	
62	5.24	male	61	the control group	13C-UBT	37.6	negative	0	
63	5.24	female	42	the control group	13C-UBT	18.2	negative	0	
64	5.27	male	39	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	30.2	negative	0	

65	5.28	female	37	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	23.3	negative	0	
66	5.28	male	30	the control group	13C-UBT	61.7	positive	56	Forgetting oral medication
67	5.29	female	42	the control group	13C-UBT	25.3	negative	4	
68	6.3	female	39	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	22.7	negative	0	
69	6.3	female	65	the control group	13C-UBT	23.6	negative	0	Poor appetite
70	6.4	male	43	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	49.5	negative	0	
71	6.4	female	39	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	15.6	negative	0	
72	6.4	male	51	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	31.6	negative	0	
73	6.7	male	27	intensive follow-up group	RUT	HP++	negative	0	
74	6.7	female	29	the control group	13C-UBT	24.9	negative	2	
75	6.7	male	25	the control group	13C-UBT	12.6	negative	0	
76	6.7	male	55	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	48.1	negative	8	
77	6.11	male	62	the control group	13C-UBT	8.4	positive	38	Forgetting oral medication

78	6.11	male	53	the control group	14C-UBT	570	negative	0	
79	6.11	female	39	the control group	13C-UBT	9	negative	0	
80	6.11	male	43	the control group	13C-UBT	46.5	negative	0	
81	6.14	female	60	the control group	13C-UBT	58.9	positive	22	Forgetting oral medication
82	6.17	male	23	the control group	13C-UBT	23.7	negative	3	
83	6.18	female	28	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	58.2	negative	0	
84	6.19	female	33	the control group	14C-UBT	880	negative	1	
85	6.2	male	56	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	38.8	negative	0	Mild nausea
86	6.2	female	56	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	61.4	negative	0	
87	6.2	male	39	the control group	13C-UBT	10	negative	6	Edema ; Abdominal distention
88	6.21	male	35	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	24.3	positive	2	
89	6.21	female	52	the control group	13C-UBT	19.3	negative	5	
90	6.24	male	48	the control group	13C-UBT	28.6	negative	0	

91	6.25	female	59	the control group	13C-UBT	32.9	negative	0	
92	6.25	female	53	the control group	13C-UBT	44	positive	125	poor appetite ;melena
93	6.26	male	45	the control group	13C-UBT	23.9	negative	0	
94	6.27	male	37	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	52.9	negative	0	
95	6.28	male	41	the control group	13C-UBT	25.1	negative	0	
96	6.28	female	26	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	41.5	withdrawn from the study	159	skin rash
97	6.28	female	31	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	21.1	negative	9	
98	7.3	female	36	the control group	13C-UBT	20.9	negative	0	
99	7.5	male	45	the control group	13C-UBT	29.2	negative	0	
100	7.5	female	53	the control group	13C-UBT	12.5	positive	15	
101	7.9	male	69	the control group	13C-UBT	28.8	negative	6	
102	7.9	male	39	the control group	13C-UBT	20.7	negative	1	Poor appetite

103	7.11	male	34	the control group	13C-UBT	11.9	positive	0	
104	7.13	male	30	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	20.6	negative	2	Abdominal distention
105	7.13	male	65	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	24.3	negative	0	
106	7.15	female	49	the control group	13C-UBT	16.2	negative	2	
107	7.15	male	33	the control group	13C-UBT	12.5	negative	2	nausea
108	7.17	female	38	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	59.8	positive	5	
109	7.17	female	64	intensive follow-up group	14C-UBT	455	negative	0	
110	7.18	male	48	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	13.9	Lost to follow-up		
111	7.18	female	45	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	48.2	negative	0	Slight diarrhea
112	7.18	female	36	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	30.3	negative	1	
113	7.22	male	63	the control group	13C-UBT	10.8	negative	0	
114	7.24	female	56	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	55.2	negative	0	
115	7.25	female	30	the control group	13C-UBT	28.7	negative	0	

116	7.25	female	53	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	45.7	negative	0	
117	7.29	female	37	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	25.8	negative	0	
118	7.30	male	55	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	64.7	negative	7	Mild nausea
119	7.30	female	23	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	7.0	negative	0	
120	8.5	female	18	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	8.7	negative	0	
121	8.5	female	24	the control group	13C-UBT	66.4	negative	0	
122	8.5	male	36	the control group	13C-UBT	54.3	negative	0	
123	8.6	male	38	the control group	13C-UBT	52.1	positive	19	Forgetting oral medication ; Diarrhea
124	8.8	female	34	the control group	13C-UBT	21.1	negative	1	
125	8.14	male	57	the control group	13C-UBT	41.5	negative	3	
126	8.14	male	40	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	19.1	negative	0	
127	8.15	male	36	the control group	13C-UBT	28.6	negative	0	Diarrhea
128	8.15	female	42	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	22.5	negative	0	

129	8.15	female	54	the control group	13C-UBT	24.9	negative	0	
130	8.20	female	29	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	19.6	negative	0	Poor appetite
131	8.20	male	49	the control group	13C-UBT	19.8	negative	0	Abdominal distention
132	8.22	female	32	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	14.0	negative	0	
133	8.22	male	56	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	40.4	negative	5	
134	8.23	male	47	the control group	14C-UBT	1467	negative	0	
135	8.27	male	37	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	66.3	negative	0	
136	8.28	female	64	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	10.2	positive	0	
137	8.29	female	35	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	30.5	negative	0	
138	9.2	female	49	the control group	13C-UBT	13.9	positive	156	bitter taste; melena
139	9.4	female	38	the control group	13C-UBT	68.2	negative	0	
140	9.4	male	39	the control group	13C-UBT	55	negative	0	
141	9.6	female	33	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	43.8	negative	0	

142	9.6	female	29	the control group	13C-UBT	19	negative	45	Not taking medication as prescribed by the doctor
143	9.24	male	62	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	26.5	negative	13	Slight diarrhea
144	9.24	male	35	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	12.3	negative	2	
145	9.24	female	59	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	32.1	negative	6	
146	9.26	male	38	the control group	RUT	HP++	negative	0	
147	9.26	female	29	the control group	13C-UBT	18.3	positive	46	Drug reduction without permission
148	9.28	female	46	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	28.4	negative	0	
149	10.8	male	39	the control group	13C-UBT	16.4	negative	0	
150	10.41	female	67	the control group	13C-UBT	79.4	negative	0	
151	10.16	male	59	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	35	negative	0	
152	10.16	male	49	the control group	13C-UBT	26.3	negative	40	Forgetting oral medication
153	10.17	male	50	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	28.2	negative	5	Abdominal distention
154	10.17	male	61	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	13.0	negative	3	

155	10.21	male	38	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	29.7	negative	0	
156	10.21	female	36	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	9.2	negative	0	
157	20.28	female	67	the control group	13C-UBT	44	negative	0	Poor appetite
158	10.30	male	56	the control group	14C-UBT	789	negative	0	
159	11.4	male	19	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	7.0	negative	0	
160	11.6	male	45	the control group	13C-UBT	33.5	negative	0	Diarrhea
161	11.6	male	47	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	83.6	negative	0	
162	11.7	male	69	the control group	RUT	HP++	negative	0	
163	11.13	female	56	the control group	13C-UBT	46.3	positive	2	
164	11.13	female	37	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	43.0	negative	0	
165	11.18	male	32	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	22.9	negative	6	Poor appetite
166	11.19	female	28	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	88.7	negative	0	
167	11.19	male	45	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	56.2	negative	0	

168	11.16	female	55	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	70.7	negative	0	
169	11.20	female	30	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	15.0	negative	0	
170	11.21	male	37	the control group	13C-UBT	29.6	negative	0	
171	11.22	male	29	the control group	13C-UBT	64	negative	0	Abdominal distention
172	11.25	female	54	the control group	13C-UBT	44.4	negative	0	
173	11.27	male	28	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	39.5	negative	0	
174	11.29	male	37	the control group	13C-UBT	16.3	positive	34	Forgetting oral medication
175	11.29	male	51	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	10.9	withdrawn from the study	128	skin rash
176	12.2	female	40	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	10.7	negative	0	
177	12.4	female	61	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	81.2	negative	0	
178	12.6	female	28	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	25.2	negative	0	
179	12.9	female	55	the control group	13C-UBT	20.2	negative	5	

180	12.10	male	25	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	27.0	negative	0	Slight diarrhea
181	12.10	male	58	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	19.7	negative	0	
182	12.11	male	42	the control group	13C-UBT	30.5	negative	8	
183	12.16	female	43	the control group	RUT	HP++	negative	0	
184	12.17	male	41	the control group	13C-UBT	26.9	positive	56	Forgetting oral medication
185	12.19	male	53	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	39.1	negative	0	
186	12.24	female	67	the control group	13C-UBT	22.6	negative	1	
187	12.24	female	39	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	45.1	negative	0	
188	12.24	male	56	the control group	13C-UBT	36.8	negative	3	
189	12.26	male	52	the control group	13C-UBT	61.2	negative	4	Diarrhea
190	12.26	male	43	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	32.7	negative	0	Mild nausea
191	12.26	female	60	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	17.8	negative	4	
192	12.27	male	23	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	24.6	negative	0	

193	12.28	female	33	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	13.6	negative	0	
194	12.28	male	56	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	25.9	negative	0	
195	12.29	male	26	the control group	13C-UBT	7.8	negative	0	
196	12.29	female	52	intensive follow-up group	13C-UBT	19.0	negative	0	